

TPS Programme Management Blog Post

Sydney Ambrose, David Sarmiento Perez, Alexandra Araujo Alvarez and Batool Almarzouq all contributed to this piece and to the Documentation Sprints.

Documentation Sprints: For the Love of Writing

In programme management, most of our days are spent writing. Emails, contracts, updating tasks, writing minutes, chasing items... but sometimes in the day to day, we aren't able to find the time for big, juicy pieces of writing. That's why the Tools, Practices & Systems Programme Management Team implemented Documentation Sprints.

What are documentation sprints?

Documentation sprints are short, focused periods of time, usually between half a day and a whole day, where the team avoids as many other meetings as possible to laser focus on the numerous documentation tasks that come with programme management. They're inspired by the Agile "sprint" practice: a time-bound period with a dedicated focus, although that's where the similarities end. This year, we've scheduled them on the last Monday of every month, in the afternoon.

The team meets online to share our goals for the session, then uses the Pomodoro technique (<https://todoist.com/productivity-methods/pomodoro-technique>): a shared timer set for 25 min bursts of work, interspersed with breaks. They're open to anyone who needs to get some focused writing and documentation done!

What do we document in documentation sprints?

The work we do in the sprints varies from session to session but can include:

- Producing templates and guides for sharing more widely, such as the Programme Management Handbook, or chapters in *The Turing Way*
- Developing Ways of work for projects: during documentation sprints we have ideated, and, after discussion with project teams, developed project specific ways of work that mix project management methodologies with projects needs. One example is the Data Safe Haven ways of work (<https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/data-safe-haven-team/blob/main/WaysOfWork.md>).
- Designing project strategy sessions
- Updates to process documents
- Drafting longer documents such as extension reports

- Implementing project learnings
- Reflecting on project communications such as newsletters and designing templates for them such as this one (https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/tps-team/blob/main/newsletters/Template_newsletter.md).

These are the kind of documentation that not only makes our team tick, but also leaves a lasting impact on the wider world.

Why do we love documentation sprints?

Documentation is important for knowledge transfer and continuity: remembering what you did 6 months ago without written contextual clues is **HARD**, never mind picking up from someone else who has moved on to another role. It's also critical for accountability and decision making, risk management, collaboration, and over all project management. However, it's often less urgent than processing expenses, running meetings, requesting invoices, chasing up interviews notes, or anything else that can crop up in the course of managing a research project at the Turing. Finding time to manage the important- but not urgent- pieces of work can be hard in a job like project management, where no two days are the same, and last minute requests often come up.

Documentation sprints offer a regular dedicated space for the team to focus on creating and updating documentation related to their projects. This helps us keep up-to-date and supports broader knowledge sharing through the creation of templates, guides, processes, and updating chapters in The Turing Way. It also provides a space for simultaneous review of documents if feedback is needed. Listening to the team's documentation goals promotes the creation of new ways of dealing with challenges that are also included in the documentation

DOCUMENTATION

Scriberia

The Turing Way project illustration by Scriberia. Used under a CC-BY 4.0 licence. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3332807.

A regular cadence of sprints has been the catalyst for developing new ways of interacting with projects, work on strategy, and lengthier writing tasks which can be hard to fit in day-to-day work. Running them as a team also aligns our priorities and helps us focus on completing the work. They're also a good team building occasion for a remote team!

We encourage teams finding that any aspect of the role is slipping down the to-do list to carve out time for a regular sprint, and to consider the benefits of sharing what you do more widely both internally and externally.